

AN ECO-FRIENDLY SMART PACKAGING FILM WITH CARREGENAAN AND ANTHOCYANIN

Emine Arman Kandirmaz, Arif Ozcan, Dogan Tutak

Marmara University, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Department of Printing
Technologies, Turkey

Original scientific paper
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10008084
earman@marmara.edu.tr

Abstract: *The basic functions of a packaging; convenience, protection, containment, and communication. While protecting the product in the package against external environmental conditions, it should also provide information about the product with the information and design on it. Research on active and smart packaging, which extends shelf life with decreasing food resources or informs when any change in food structure occurs, attracts more and more attention. The use of natural resources in food traceability (in smart packaging) is very beneficial for health. The fact that polylactic acid is a material of natural origin and its use in food and medicine by the U.S. FDA suggests that it is a very good raw material for the smart packaging industry. Anthocyanins are a naturally sourced material that changes color with pH obtained from plants such as grape skin, red cabbage, strawberries, and turnips. When foods spoil, they release amine derivatives into the environment, which causes shifts in the packaging towards the base. In this study, anthocyanins were extracted from natural sources and carregenaan's films containing these anthocyanins was prepared by solvent casting method. The color properties of the prepared films were determined by both color spectrophotometer and UV spectrophotometer. The surface morphologies of smart films were examined using SEM. The swelling ratio, re-release in water, optical, and mechanical properties were determined. The use of the obtained films as smart films was determined on chicken. As a result, smart films have been produced successfully. The resulting smart films turn red-violet in acidic conditions and blue-green in basic conditions. It has been determined that the film, which changes color with deterioration, can be used as a smart packaging material.*

Keywords: smart packaging, anthocyanin, carregenaan, colorimetric indicators, food quality

1 INTRODUCTION

The deterioration of chicken meat depends on the microorganism activities that reproduce on it. As a result of these activities, permanent and undesirable changes occur in the structure of chicken meat, these changes are called "deterioration". The most important factor that increases the deterioration rate of chicken meat from the production to the end consumer is the temperature conditions during storage. Because microorganisms operating on chicken meat can survive at certain temperature values. For this reason, chicken meat is kept in the cold chain and the deterioration time is extended. However, breaks in the cold chain will cause the meat to deteriorate before the expiration date (Petruzzi et al., 2017). For this reason, many studies have been carried out on active and smart packaging in recent years. In traditional packaging, the primary purpose is to make the product act as a barrier to protect it from moisture, light, air, impurities, and physical damage. Active packaging provides the extension of shelf life with chemical modifications made in conventional packaging materials. Smart packaging, on the other hand, does not have an effect on extending the shelf life of the product, but they are markers that can show the changes in the product environment and the structure of the product with color changes (Park et al., 2013). As an example of smart packaging; lactic acid-based time-temperature indicators (Hidayat et al., 2017), binary color indicators (Chen et al., 2017), salmonella biosensors (Rukchon et al., 2014), colorimetric mixed-pH dye-based indicators (Brizio and Prentice, 2014), photochromic time-temperature indicators (Saliu and Della Pergola, 2018), carbon dioxide indicators (Quested et al., 2011) can be displayed.

The main function of traditional food packaging includes reducing food spoilage (thus extending shelf life), maintaining quality and safety, and reducing/eliminating physical damage to food. Packaging serves to protect the contents from factors such as heat, light, humidity, pressure, oxygen, enzymes, microorganisms, odours, insects, dust, and dirt. The traditional secondary function of food packaging is the marketing of the product. In recent years, it has increasingly demonstrated the importance of packaging as a natural part of marketing. Although it performs a secondary function, this aspect of food packaging has a direct impact on the sales of the product. However, a significant problem of food waste and increasing consumer demands for lightly preserved, fresh-tasting, convenient foods as well as changing retail practices (i.e., the globalization of food distribution) are beginning to emerge (Butler, 2001)

Although the potential advantages of smart packaging are numerous, there are concerns about the use of smart packaging. At a time when consumers are becoming more aware of the environmental impacts from the use of excessive non-biodegradable plastics, concerns have been expressed about the increased amount of packaging that may be required for the widespread use of smart packaging (Taoukis et al., 1999). One of the most convenient ways to incorporate smart packaging technologies into food and beverage packaging is with smart labels. The functionality of smart tags is typically in the form of inks that are chemically formulated to interact with the surrounding environment. The working principle of smart labels is mechanical, chemical, enzymatic or microbiological irreversible change, usually expressed as a visible response in the form of mechanical deformation, color development or color movement (Zhao et al., 2017). Chemical or physical reactions are caused by chemical reactions or acid base reactions, melting, polymerization etc. It is based on physical changes such as time and temperature. The color-based pH indicator is a promising indicator to be used in the detection of microbial metabolites of food freshness. This method is used as a label on the package to monitor food freshness. These labels work based on pH changes because the total volatile basic nitrogen (TVBN) produced during food spoilage inside the package cavity causes a pH increase resulting in the indicator color changing and easily detectable with the naked eye. Smart packaging techniques, which have been increasingly used in recent years, are systems that show the conditions that packaged foods are exposed to during transportation and storage, and they are used as an indicator of inside and outside the packaging, especially during distribution and storage, to protect the quality characteristics of the food and to ensure food safety.

Anthocyanins are an important type of water-soluble flavonoid pigment that gives the roots, leaves, seeds, stems, flowers, fruits, and other organs of various plants a wide range of distinctive colors from purple, blue, pink and red. These colorants, which have low toxicity, are frequently used in the pharmaceutical, food and cosmetic industries (Çoruhli, 2013). Anthocyanins, water-soluble polar compounds, are highly sensitive molecules sensitive to some factors. For this reason, their stability and color change in the presence of those factors. These include sulfur dioxide, oxygen, metallic ions, copigments, ascorbic acid, protein, sugar, light, heat, and pH (Ersus and Yurdagel, 2007). Most anthocyanins turn blue under low basic condition and red under acidic condition. The use of anthocyanins as acid-base indicators is based on these properties. Anthocyanins have been found in fruits such as blueberry, blackberry, cherry, raspberry, blood orange, red grape, apple, peach, strawberry, watermelon, carrot, cabbage, purple onion, red bean, pepper, tomato, and similar colored vegetables (Lila, 2004).

In this study, it was aimed to develop a natural freshness indicator label that can indicate the deterioration of chicken meat over time based on volatile ammonia and biochemical amine type compounds formed from chicken meat, and therefore pH change.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Black carrot was obtained from a local market. Carregenaan, acid, base, and solvents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.2 Methods

Obtaining anthocyanin from black carrot was done according to the literature (Ağçam and Akyildiz, 2015). 5g samples were taken from the homogenized black carrot pulp, transferred to a 50 mL Teflon tube, and 20 mL of distile was added as an extraction solution, mixed, and kept at room conditions for 5 min. Following this, the mixture in the tube was vortexed at high speed for 30 seconds and then centrifuged (4000 rpm, 4°C, 10 min). The clear part obtained after centrifugation was transferred to a 50 mL flask and the pulp residue was extracted a second time under the same conditions. The clear portions were combined and made up to the volume of the balloon with the same extraction solution. The clear colored solutions obtained were removed from their solvents in the evaporator and dried in a vacuum oven at room temperature.

The color properties of the obtained anthocyanins were investigated by shimadzu UV spectrophotometer at different pHs. Smart tag films were created by using the obtained anthocyanins and carregenaan in the ratios in Table 1.

For the preparation of smart film, firstly 10% carregenaan solution was prepared in water. Obtained anthocyanin was added to the prepared solution in the ratios in Table 1 and mixed rapidly, and film formulations were prepared.

Table 1. Smart label formulations.

Chemical structure	%10 Carregenaan solution (%)	Anthocyanin (%)
<i>F0</i>	100	0
<i>F1</i>	99	1
<i>F2</i>	97.5	2.5
<i>F3</i>	95	5

The resulting equal volumes of film mixtures were poured into the Teflon mold and set in 10 minutes at room temperature in vacuum oven.

2.3 Characterization

The color character of the anthocyanin was determined by Shimadzu UV-2450 model UV-VIS spectrophotometer. The surface properties of the films were determined with Philips XL30 ESEM-FEG/EDAX. Thickness of the films was measured using a digital micrometer (Mitotuyo 7327, Tokyo, Japan). The mean value was taken from ten replications across each film sample. Tensile tests of the produced films were determined standard tensile stress-strain tests to measure modules, ultimate tensile strength, and elongation at break. Standard tensile stress-strain experiments were performed at room temperature on a Materials Testing Machine Z010/TN2S, using a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min.

The color measurements of obtained films were made by CIEL*a*b* method using X-Rite eXact spectrophotometer according to ISO 12647-2:2013 standard. The measurement conditions of the spectrophotometer are determined as polarization filter with 0°/45° geometry with 2 observer angle with D50 light source in the range of 400-700 nm. The difference between the colors of the different films were calculated according to formula 1 according to the CIE ΔE 2000 ISO 13655 standard.

$$\Delta E_{00} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta L'}{k_L S_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta C'}{k_C S_C}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta H'}{k_H S_H}\right)^2} + R_T \frac{\Delta C'}{k_C S_C} \frac{\Delta H'}{k_H S_H} \quad (1)$$

The obtained films were wrapped on tomatoes and the related tomatoes were kept at room temperature. The deterioration of tomatoes was evaluated visually and colorimetrically.

3 RESULTS

Anthocyanins were successfully extracted from black carrots. The color of the obtained anthocyanin solutions at different pHs is given in Figure 1. When foods such as chicken decompose, they release nitrogen-containing compounds into the environment, which causes the pH to shift to the basic environment around the food. When the anthocyanins extracted in this study were examined at different pHs (Figure 1), it was observed that the color turned pink at acidic pHs, purple-blue at basic pHs, and gray-green in extremely basic conditions.

Figure 1. Color change of extracted anthocyanin.

The color characters of the obtained extracts were examined by UV spectroscopy at pH 1-2-5-7-8 and are given in Figure 2. When the pHs obtained are in acidic condition, a broad anthocyanin peak is observed around 520 nm. However, this peak disappears as the pH shifts towards the base. The results obtained are compatible with the literature (Kammerer et al., 2004).

Figure 2. UV spectrums of anthocyanin in different pH.

Caragennan binder biofilms were produced by using the obtained extract at different rates. The films produced were placed in a petri dish with chicken bought from the local market and kept at +4 C. At the end of 4 days, the change in color was measured with x-rite spectrophotometer and the results are given in Table 2. When the table was examined, it was determined that the label color changed from pink-red to purple-blue at the end of 4 days. When the color properties were examined, it was determined that the shift to b in the basic case confirmed the blue shift. The fact that the difference between the two colors

obtained is above 3 in ΔE indicates that the color difference is at a perceptible level. the films that show values higher gloss values.

Table 2. Optical characteristic of smart labels due to chicken spoilage.

	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE	Gloss
Color before decay	30	15	5	-	15.30
Color after decay	23	7	-1	9.48	15.20

The surface properties of the films obtained were determined by SEM (Figure 3). When the SEM photograph is examined, it is seen that the films have a smooth surface and are homogeneous.

Figure 3. SEM image of anthocyanin-carregenaan film.

Carregenaan films were immersed in water for 24 h at 25°C. Swollen films were then putted between two dry papers to remove residual liquids from the smart label surface, after that weighed, dried in a vacuum oven, and reweighed. The water contents of smart labels were calculated using eq. (2).

$$\text{Water content (\%)} = (W_s - W_d) / W_s \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where W_s : weights of swollen films and W_d : vacuum-dried films.

The swelling characteristics of the films obtained were examined and it was determined that 15% swelling occurred in the films due to the hydrophilic structure of carregenaan. However, with this swelling, the anthocyanin

molecules did not pass into the water sample and fulfilled the smart label function.

Carregenaan films were weighed after vacuum-drying, then immersed in a water for 24h. The samples taken from the water were examined by UV spectroscopy and it was investigated whether the anthocyanin peak at 520nm exists or not, whether the film releases the active substance or not. According to the data obtained, it was determined that there was no back-release in contact with water for 24 hours. Results are line with literature (Roh and Shin, 2006).

The thickness of the produced films was determined as 0.178 ± 0.02 mm. In addition, the tensile strength was determined as 3.150 ± 0.15 kg/mm². This results shows that carregenaan film is stronger.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Anthocyanin was successfully extracted and films containing carregenaan were stably prepared. The films obtained have good mechanical properties and no re-release in water occurred from the film for 24 hours. The films proved that they can be used to determine chicken degradation colorimetrically depending on the pH, with the color change from pink to purple.

5 REFERENCES

- Ağçam, E., & Akyıldız, A. (2015). Siyah havuç posasından antosiyaninlerin ekstraksiyonuna farklı çözügen ve asit konsantrasyonlarının etkileri. *Gıda*, 40(3), 149-156.
- Brizio, A.P.D.R., & Prentice, C. (2014). Use of smart photochromic indicator for dynamic monitoring of the shelf life of chilled chicken based products. *Meat Sci.*, 96(3), 1219-1226.
- Butler, P. (2001). Smart packaging—intelligent packaging for food, beverages, pharmaceuticals and household products. *Mater. World*, 9(3), 11-13.
- Chen, I.H., Horikawa, S., Bryant, K., Riggs, R., Chin, B.A., & Barbaree, J.M. (2017). Bacterial assessment of phage magnetoelastic sensors for *Salmonella enterica* Typhimurium detection in chicken meat. *Food Control*, 71, 273-278.
- Çoruhlu, T. (2013). Kara dut antosiyaninlerinin iyonik jelasyon yöntemi ile enkapsülasyonu ve enkapsülasyon parametrelerinin tepki yüzeyi metodu ile optimize edilmesi (Doctoral dissertation, Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü).

- Ersus, S., & Yurdagel, U. (2007). Microencapsulation of anthocyanin pigments of black carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) by spray drier. *J. Food Eng.*, 80(3), 805-812.
- Hidayat, M.A., Puspitaningtyas, N., Gani, A.A., & Kuswandi, B. (2017). Rapid test for the determination of total phenolic content in brewed-filtered coffee using colorimetric paper. *J. Food Sci. Technol.*, 54, 3384-3390.
- Kammerer, D., Carle, R., & Schieber, A. (2004). Quantification of anthocyanins in black carrot extracts (*Daucus carota* ssp. *sativus* var. *atrorubens* Alef.) and evaluation of their color properties. *Eur. Food Res. Technol.*, 219, 479-486.
- Lila, M.A. (2004). Anthocyanins and human health: an in vitro investigative approach. *J. Biotechnol. Biomed.*, 2004(5), 306.
- Park, H.R., Kim, Y.A., Jung, S.W., Kim, H.C., & Lee, S.J. (2013). Response of microbial time temperature indicator to quality indices of chicken breast meat during storage. *Food Sci. Biotechnol.*, 22, 1145-1152.
- Petruzzi, L., Corbo, M.R., Sinigaglia, M., & Bevilacqua, A. (2017). Microbial spoilage of foods: Fundamentals. In *The microbiological quality of food* (pp. 1-21). Woodhead Publishing.
- Quested, T.E., Parry, A.D., Easteal, S., & Swannell, R. (2011). Food and drink waste from households in the UK.
- Roh, Y.H., & Shin, C.S. (2006). Preparation and characterization of alginate-carrageenan complex films. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 99(6), 3483-3490.
- Rukchon, C., Nopwinyuwong, A., Trevanich, S., Jinkarn, T., & Suppakul, P. (2014). Development of a food spoilage indicator for monitoring freshness of skinless chicken breast. *Talanta*, 130, 547-554.
- Saliu, F., & Della Pergola, R. (2018). Carbon dioxide colorimetric indicators for food packaging application: Applicability of anthocyanin and poly-lysine mixtures. *Sens. Actuators B Chem.*, 258, 1117-1124.
- Taoukis, P.S., Koutsoumanis, K., & Nychas, G.J.E. (1999). Use of time-temperature integrators and predictive modelling for shelf life control of chilled fish under dynamic storage conditions. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.*, 53(1), 21-31.
- Zhao, L., Temelli, F., & Chen, L. (2017). Encapsulation of anthocyanin in liposomes using supercritical carbon dioxide: Effects of anthocyanin and sterol concentrations. *J. Funct. Foods*, 34, 159-167.